

On the solubility of methane in water: some useful results for hydrate nucleation

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ABSTRACT: In this paper the solubility of methane in water along the 400 bar isobar is determined by computer simulations using the TIP4P/Ice force field for water and a simple LJ model for methane. In particular, the solubility of methane in water when in contact with the gas phase, and the solubility of methane in water when in contact with the hydrate has been determined. The solubility of methane in a gas-liquid system decreases as temperature increases. The solubility of methane in a hydrate-liquid system increases with temperature. The two curves intersect at a certain temperature that determines the triple point T_3 at a certain pressure. We also determined T_3 by the three phases direct coexistence method. The results of both methods agree and we suggest 295(2) K as the value of T_3 for this system. We also analyzed the impact of curvature on the solubility of methane in water. We found that the presence of curvature increases the solubility in both the gas-liquid and the hydrate-liquid systems. The change in chemical potential for the formation of hydrate is evaluated along the isobar using two different thermodynamic routes obtaining good agreement between them. It is shown that the driving force for hydrate nucleation under experimental conditions is higher than that for the formation of pure ice when compared at the same supercooling. We also show that supersaturation (i.e. concentrations above those of the planar interface) increases the driving force for nucleation dramatically. The effect of bubbles can be equivalent to that of an additional supercooling of about 20 K. Having highly supersaturated homogeneous solutions make possible the spontaneous formation of the hydrate at temperatures as high as 285 K (i.e ten degrees below T_3). The crucial role of the concentration of methane for hydrate formation is clearly revealed. Nucleation of the hydrate can be either impossible or easy and fast depending on the concentration of methane which seems to play the leading role in the understanding of the kinetics of hydrate formation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydrates are compounds formed when water is in contact with a gas phase of a small molecule (i.e methane or carbon dioxide) at moderate to high pressures and at low temperatures.¹ The molecules of water form an open structure and the guest molecules of the gas occupy the lattice positions (although in nature the gas hydrates are not completely occupied). The simplest hydrate structure is denoted as sI¹ and is the one formed by methane and carbon dioxide. The unit cell of the sI solid belongs to the cubic system. Hydrates are of interest both from a fundamental point of view and from a practical point of view.¹ Hydrates are found close to the shores of the coast and one could obtain natural gas from them. From a fundamental point of view they are formed from a mixture of rather small and simple molecules.

Over the last few years we have studied in detail the nucleation in a number of systems.²⁻⁶ We have implemented the technique of seeding⁴ which allows one to estimate nucleation rates by combining simulations results

and classical nucleation theory. The technique of seeding has been applied successfully to a number of systems from simple ones such as hard spheres (HS) and Lennard-Jones (LJ) to more complex such as water or salty water⁷ obtaining good agreement with results obtained from more rigorous techniques. It would be interesting to extend the methodology of seeding to more complex systems as is the case of hydrates. In fact, in 2012 Molinero et al. implemented the technique of seeding⁸ to obtain a first estimate of the nucleation rate of hydrates using the mW model of water.⁹

Before considering nucleation using seeding there are some issues that should be solved. First of all the estimate of the temperature at a certain pressure at which the three phases can coexist is needed. Conde and Vega¹⁰ suggested in 2011 to use direct coexistence of the three phases to estimate T_3 . It was observed that combining TIP4P/Ice¹¹ and a simple LJ model for methane gives the estimates of T_3 that are in good agreement with the experimental ones (the same was found by Míguez et al. in a later study on carbon dioxide hydrates¹²). Notice that to obtain values of T_3 in good agreement with experiment, water models with a good prediction of the experimental melting point of ice Ih are required.¹³ After this study a number of groups have revisited the problem

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using the same force field.^{14–18} Although the agreement between different groups is reasonable, some differences still exist, with values of T_3 at 400 bar being in the range of 290–300 K for this force field. It would be of interest before addressing nucleation studies to reach some consensus on the value of T_3 for this system.

The solubility of methane in water increases as the temperature decreases. This has been studied both in experiments and in simulation.^{19,20} However, the solubility of methane from the hydrate is rarely studied either in experiments or in simulations.²¹ In this work we shall perform a study of the solubility of the hydrate. It will be shown that solubility studies allow us to estimate T_3 . Thus in principle the values of T_3 obtained from the direct coexistence of the three phases and those of the solubility should be coincident. We shall show that this is the case, and that they are the same to within the estimated uncertainty which is of about 2 K.

A key quantity in Classical Nucleation Theory (CNT) is the driving force for nucleation, which is denoted as $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$. This is the change in chemical potential of the "reaction" where a molecule of the hydrate is formed from the molecules of methane and water both in the aqueous solution. Although it would be possible to determine $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ from experiments often this is not possible due to the lack of information about the thermodynamic properties of the system (i.e. enthalpies, volumes, etc). Estimates of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ are rare with the exception of the work of Kashchiev and Firoozabadi.^{22,23} In this work we shall address the issue of the evaluation of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ using two slightly different thermodynamic routes. Results of both routes will be coincident (within the combined error bar).

An interesting issue is whether one can modify the driving force for nucleation artificially.²⁴ The analysis reveals that the concentration of methane dramatically affects the value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$. In general, increasing the concentration of methane increases the driving force for nucleation. We found, in agreement with the work of other authors,^{25,26} that bubbles increase the solubility of methane, and we will quantitatively estimate the impact of this increment in solubility on the driving force for nucleation. It will be shown that bubbles increase the driving force, but there is a limit, as it is not possible to have bubbles which are mechanically stable below a certain size of about 1.2 nm radius. However, we will show that another strategy is possible by generating homogeneous supersaturated solutions in which the nucleation of methane hydrates can occur even at temperatures just 10 K below T_3 . Also it will be shown that the solubility of methane in water when solution is in contact with the hydrate also increases by introducing curvature in the interface.

Thus in this paper we address the first steps towards addressing the issue of the homogeneous nucleation of hydrates under experimental conditions with special interest in T_3 and in $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$. It can be said that the study of the solubility of methane in water (either from

the gas or from the hydrate) contains a lot of interesting physics and the key ingredients to understand hydrate nucleation in future studies following the increasing activity in the field of the last years.^{8,27–41}

II. METHODS

All of the results presented in this work were obtained using classical molecular dynamics (MD). Simulations were performed using the GROMACS package^{42,43} in the NpT ensemble. Three types of barostats were used depending on the problem. Either isotropic NpT (where the three sides of the simulation box change proportionally), anisotropic NpT (where each side changed independently) or Np_zT (where only one size of the simulation box was allowed to fluctuate) simulations will be performed in this work. A time step of 2 fs was used. To keep the temperature constant, the Nose-Hoover thermostat^{44,45} was employed, with a coupling constant of 2 ps. The pressure was kept constant with the use of the Parrinello-Rahman barostat,⁴⁶ the time constant used was equal to 2 ps. For all of the simulations the pressure was equal to 400 bar. For electrostatic and van der Waals interaction a cut-off of 9 Å was used. Coulombic interactions were treated using the PME method.⁴⁷ Long range energy corrections to energy and pressure were included to the Lennard-Jones part of the potential. For water, the TIP4P-Ice¹¹ water model was used, while for methane the parameters were taken from Ref. 48 and 49. For cross-interaction between TIP4P-Ice water and methane models Lorentz-Berthelot rules were applied. In order to maintain the geometry of water molecules in the systems, the LINCS algorithm^{50,51} was employed.

For simplicity throughout this paper the phase of pure methane will be denoted as "gas phase", as in the literature one often uses the term "gas hydrates" even though methane is studied at supercritical conditions. In certain cases we have simulated the solid phase of the hydrate with structure sI ($Pm\bar{3}n$) with a lattice constant of about 12 Å. In this solid⁵² one has 8 molecules of methane and 46 molecules of water in the unit cell (i.e. the ratio of water to methane molecules is 5.75). The 8 molecules of methane occupy the eight cavities available in the solid structure (2 of them being smaller than the other six). Oxygens occupy the crystallographic positions $c(6)$, $k(24)$ and $i(16)$ whereas the methane occupy the $d(6)$ and $a(2)$ crystallographic positions. We used full occupancy (i.e. all cages are occupied by methane molecules). Experimentally occupancies around 95 per cent are often found.^{1,53} In the hydrate structure one finds proton disorder. Proton disordered configurations satisfying the Bernal Fowler rules⁵⁴ were generated using the algorithm of Buch et al.⁵⁵

To analyze the melting of the hydrate or its stability with time we shall determine the size of the largest solid cluster of the hydrate (i.e. we shall compute the number of molecules of water forming the hydrate). For this

purpose we shall use the order parameter proposed by Lechner and Dellago.⁵⁶ We found that \bar{q}_3 was a reasonable order parameter (notice that for ice Ih we used⁵⁷ \bar{q}_6 but this is not a good order parameter for hydrate formation, as noted by Algaba et al.⁵⁸). While \bar{q}_3 may not be the optimal order parameter as many other choices have been proposed for hydrates,⁵⁹⁻⁶¹ it is reasonable, simple and adequate for our purpose of detecting molecules of the solid phase. Details about the implementation of \bar{q}_3 and the threshold value used to label a molecule as solid are provided in Supporting Information.

Since the solubility of methane in water is small we shall use the unsymmetrical convention⁶² in the thermodynamic description of mixtures so that we will have a dominant component (solvent) which in this case will be water and a minor component (solute) which in this case will be methane. The chemical potential of water in the mixture is given by:⁶³

$$\mu_{H_2O}(p, T, x_{H_2O}) = \mu_{H_2O}^*(p, T) + kT \ln(\gamma_{H_2O} \cdot x_{H_2O}) \quad (1)$$

where x_{H_2O} is the molar fraction of water, and $\mu_{H_2O}^*(T, p)$ (i.e the standard state for water) is the chemical potential of pure water at the same T and p of the mixture. γ_{H_2O} is the activity coefficient of water. The chemical potential of methane in the aqueous solution is given by:

$$\mu_{CH_4}(p, T, x_{CH_4}) = \mu_{CH_4}^0(p, T) + kT \ln(\gamma_{CH_4} \cdot x_{CH_4}) \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_{CH_4}^0(T, p)$ is the standard state of methane which depends on T and p but not on composition. Notice that the standard state of water is a "real" state as it corresponds to pure water at the same T and p. However, the standard state of methane is a "virtual" state as it does not correspond to any physical realization. It corresponds to a "virtual" state of pure methane where intermolecular interactions are identical to those obtained at infinite dilution. From a statistical mechanics point of view $\mu_{CH_4}^0(p, T)$ is related to the residual chemical potential of methane in water at infinite dilution (after adding the constant $kT \ln(\rho_{H_2O} \cdot \Lambda_{CH_4}^3 \cdot q_{CH_4})$ where ρ_{H_2O} is the number density of pure water, Λ_{CH_4} is the thermal de Broglie wavelength of methane and q_{CH_4} is the ideal gas partition function of methane containing all degrees of freedom but translation) and can also be related to the Henry's constant.⁶⁴ In the unsymmetrical convention it holds that when $x_{H_2O} \rightarrow 1$ both γ_{H_2O} and γ_{CH_4} go to one.⁶² Since the solubility of methane in water is quite small, it is reasonable (although not exact) to assume that the activity coefficient both for methane and water are close to one. We shall assume that this is the case in our "approximate" treatment of the aqueous solution of methane.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

III.A. Solubility of methane in water from the gas phase

By using the direct coexistence method we shall compute the solubility of methane in water for several temperatures along the 400 bar isobar. For that purpose a slab of water (2959 molecules) was put in contact with a slab of gas (methane, 922 molecules) with an initial size of the simulation box of around $3.6 \times 3.6 \times 14.4 \text{ nm}^3$. The planar interface is located in the XY plane and pressure is applied perpendicular to the interface using the Np_zT ensemble. Simulations were run for more than 500 ns and averages were obtained using the last 250 ns (typically 100-150 ns were required to reach the equilibrium concentration). From the simulations we also obtained the surface tension of the water-methane interface using the pressure tensor⁶⁵:

$$\sigma(\text{planar}) = \frac{L_z}{2} \left(p_{zz} - \frac{p_{xx} + p_{yy}}{2} \right) \quad (3)$$

Results for the surface tension are presented in Table 1. Notice that our results are only qualitative as to obtain precise values of this magnitude a large cutoff and/or the inclusion of long range corrections are needed. Using the methodology of Lundberg and Edholm⁶⁶ (which has been shown to work properly by Blazquez et al.⁶⁷), we roughly estimated a long range correction of about 2 mJ/m^2 . Moreover for five temperatures we repeated the runs using a much larger cutoff (i.e 17 \AA) and the results are also presented in Table 1. It is confirmed that the values of σ for larger cutoff are around $1.5\text{-}2 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ higher than those presented in Table 1 for the cutoff used in this work (i.e 9 \AA).

In Fig. 1 the solubilities of methane in water along the isobar are shown. As can be seen the solubility decreases as the temperature increases. The solubility is small and the molar fraction was never larger than 0.02 (in molar fraction). We did not observe the formation of hydrate in any of the runs. Additionally, we evaluated the solubility at five temperatures using a larger cutoff (i.e 17 \AA). As can be seen the use of a larger cutoff reduces slightly (by 5-10 percent) the solubility of methane in the aqueous phase. It should be mentioned that the solubility of water in the methane gas is negligible. To a good approximation the gas phase is pure methane and in this work we have not computed the solubility of water in methane since it is at least one order of magnitude lower than that of methane in water.

In Fig. 1 the experimental value of the solubility of methane in water at temperature of 303 K and pressure of 400 bar is also shown.⁶⁸ As can be seen, the value that we obtained reproduces the experimental value reasonably well. It is true, however, that the agreement between simulation and experimental results could be improved by introducing a small scaling factor to the default Lorentz-Berthelot combination rule.

TABLE 1. Interfacial free energy σ (for a planar interface) between methane gas and an aqueous solution at $p=400$ bar obtained at different temperatures. Values of σ are in mJ/m^2 . The values with an asterisk were obtained using a cutoff of 17 \AA . The error of the values of σ is of about $0.4 \text{ mJ}/\text{m}^2$.

T/K	$\sigma/ \text{mJ}/\text{m}^2$	$\sigma^*/ \text{mJ}/\text{m}^2$
250	62.8	
260	61.8	63.1
270	61.5	
280	61.0	62.2
290	60.4	
300	59.6	61.4
310	59.1	

FIG. 1. Solubility of methane in water when the solution is in contact with the gas phase at $p = 400$ bar. For each T the results of two (three in the case of 250 K) independent runs are shown to provide some idea of the uncertainty of our calculations. For five temperatures (open green circles) we computed the solubility using a larger cutoff (i.e 17 \AA). For comparison, an experimental value of methane in water at 303 K of Wang et.al⁶⁸ is also presented (orange point). Lines are a guide to the eye.

It goes without saying that when the system reaches equilibrium, the temperature in the two phases is the same, the pressure is the same (as one has a planar interface) and the chemical potential of methane in water is the same, so that it holds that:

$$\mu_{CH_4}^I(p, T, x_{CH_4}^I) = \mu_{CH_4}^{II}(p, T, x_{CH_4}^{II}) \quad (4)$$

$$\mu_{H_2O}^I(p, T, x_{CH_4}^I) = \mu_{H_2O}^{II}(p, T, x_{CH_4}^{II}) \quad (5)$$

where the superscripts I and II label the two phases at equilibrium. Since we are dealing with a two component system having methane and water, the molar fraction of one of them (for instance methane) is enough to describe

the composition of the mixture (as the sum of the molar fraction of methane and water is one). There is an interesting consequence of the equations 4 and 5. As the gas phase is basically pure methane, and as the chemical potential is the same in the two phases, one can obtain easily the chemical potential of methane in the water solution by computing that of pure methane in the gas phase (i.e neglecting the very small presence of water in the gas phase). Therefore we shall use the approximation:

$$\mu_{CH_4}^I(p, T, x_{CH_4}^I) = \mu_{CH_4}^{II}(p, T, x_{CH_4}^{II} = 1) \quad (6)$$

where phase I is the aqueous phase, and phase II is the gas phase (which we shall assume is pure methane).

The change in chemical potential of methane along an isobar can be obtained from the thermodynamic relation:

$$\left(\frac{\partial(\mu_{CH_4}/T)}{\partial T} \right)_p = - \frac{h_{CH_4}}{T^2} \quad (7)$$

For reasons that will be clear later, let us set the chemical potential of pure methane at 400 bar to zero at a certain reference temperature T_{ref} . Then we can integrate the previous equation to obtain:

$$\mu_{CH_4}(T)/(k_B T) = - \int_{T_{ref}}^T \frac{h_{CH_4}}{k T'^2} dT' \quad (8)$$

where μ_{CH_4} is the chemical potential of methane and h_{CH_4} is its partial molar enthalpy (either per molecule when using k in the denominator or per mole when using R in the denominator). Of course in the case of a pure substance the partial molar enthalpy is simply the molar enthalpy. By performing simulations of pure methane along the 400 bar isobar we can compute the enthalpy and using the previous equation we can compute the chemical potential of methane. We shall not include the kinetic energy when computing the enthalpy (i.e $3/2 k_B T$ in the case of methane) as this term cancels out when computing chemical potential differences evaluated at constant T and p. Results for the chemical potential of methane as a function of T are presented in Fig. 2 (where we have selected for reasons that will be discussed later $T_{ref} = 295 \text{ K}$).

An interesting question is whether there is any possible temperature limit to perform the simulations to compute the solubility. As we did not observe nucleation of the hydrate the simulations can be performed at any temperature without any difficulty although of course as the temperature decreases the dynamics slows down and equilibration is more difficult.

FIG. 2. Chemical potential of bulk methane obtained along the isobar $p = 400$ bar. We arbitrarily set the value of the chemical potential to zero at the temperature $T = 295$ K.

III.B. Solubility of methane in water from the hydrate phase

We shall also compute the solubility of methane in water when the solution is in contact with the hydrate along the 400 bar isobar. For that purpose we shall use the direct coexistence method. A slab of the hydrate will be put in contact with water solution. The dimensions of the simulation box were $4.8 \times 4.8 \times 8.7 \text{ nm}^3$ (with about 3000 molecules of water in the hydrate and 3000 molecules of water in the solution and with a total number of 445 molecules of methane most of them (but not all) in the hydrate). We used complete occupancy of the methane in the cages of the hydrate structure. Again the interface was located in the XY plane and the Z axis was perpendicular to the interface. An anisotropic barostat was applied along the three axis so that the dimensions of the simulation box could change independently. The pressures used were identical and equal to 400 bar in all three directions. The anisotropic barostat was important to remove any stress in the solid and to obtain the correct solubility. Simulations were performed for temperatures in the range of 250 - 330 K. The length of the simulations was greater than 500 ns in all cases. The averages were obtained after removing the first 250 ns. It should be mentioned that to evaluate the solubility of methane in water when in contact with the hydrate it is convenient to use an initial configuration with a concentration of methane in water not too far from the equilibrium value to reach equilibrium as fast as possible. For all temperatures we performed two runs, the first one to estimate the value of the solubility and the second one to determine it with high accuracy. When equilibrium is reached the chemical potential of the two components (water and methane) is the same in the two phases, the temperature is the same, and the pressure is the same (as we have a planar interface).

Results for the solubility of methane when solution is in contact with the hydrate are presented in Fig. 3. As

can be seen the solubility of methane increases with temperature. We were able to obtain the solubility from low temperatures up to a temperature of 330 K. At the temperature of 340 K it was not possible to determine the solubility since the hydrate melted. The melting was a two step process. Firstly in the liquid phase a bubble of pure methane nucleated spontaneously. After that the methane of the aqueous solution moved quickly to the bubble, and the methane from the hydrate moved to the aqueous solution provoking the melting of the hydrate. Thus there is a kinetic limit at high temperatures to determine the solubility of methane from the hydrate.

FIG. 3. Solubility of methane in water when in contact with the hydrate phase at $p = 400$ bar. For five temperatures (open blue circles) we computed the solubility using a larger cutoff (i.e 17 Å). Dashed lines are a guide to the eye.

Some plots of the solubility of the hydrate as a function of temperature (for pressures different from the one considered in this work) were described in an experimental paper²¹ but to the best of our knowledge were never reported in simulations.

III.C. Three phases coexistence from solubility calculations

It is now interesting to plot both solubility curves (the solubility of methane in water from the gas, and the solubility of methane in water from the hydrate) in the same plot. This is done in Fig. 4. As can be seen there is a temperature at which these solubility curves cross. At the crossing point the aqueous phase has the same composition and it is in equilibrium simultaneously with the gas phase and with the hydrate. Therefore it is a triple point where the three phases are at equilibrium. This temperature will be denoted as T_3 . To the best of our knowledge this is the first time T_3 is determined from solubility calculations of two independent two phase coexistence runs. However, this method is routinely used in the context of classical equations of state to determine

three-phase coexistence conditions for gas and/or solid phases.^{69–71}

The value obtained from our calculations for T_3 is 297(2) K. Our value is consistent with the values reported by other groups using the three phases coexistence approach^{10,14,16,17}. A comprehensive study of the impact of the cutoff of the potential on T_3 is beyond the scope of this work as it will require using a much larger cutoff or even to use PME methods to properly account for the LJ interactions and that will make the calculations terribly expensive. However, we have included in Fig. 4 the solubilities of methane from the gas phase in water and from the hydrate phase in water at several temperatures using a much larger cutoff (i.e 17 Å). The solubility of methane from the hydrate is hardly affected by the value of the cutoff, whereas that from the gas phase is reduced indicating that the impact of the truncation of the potential is more important when the two phases differ significantly in density. With the larger cutoff the intersection of the two solubility curves occurs at 295(2) K.

FIG. 4. Solubilities of methane from the gas and from the hydrate along the isobar $p = 400$ bar. The crossing of the two lines determines the triple point temperature T_3 at 400 bar. The solubilities of methane when in contact with bubbles of methane of different radius (given in nm) are also shown as orange squares. For five temperatures we computed the solubilities of methane from the gas phase (open green circles) and hydrate (open light blue circles) using a larger cutoff (i.e 17 Å). The light blue square is the solubility of methane when the hydrate is forming a spherical cluster.

The summary is that solubility calculations are also a (relatively simple) route to T_3 . Let us discuss briefly the advantages and disadvantages of this approach. The advantage of this methodology (with respect to the three phases method) is that the simulations reach equilibrium and one needs to simulate two phases (rather than three). From a computational point of view it could be a little bit cheaper as 500 ns are usually enough to reach equilibrium whereas in the three phases method one may need

runs of the order of the microsecond or more to clearly detect melting/growing of the methane hydrate. In addition to that, the three phases method exhibits some degree of stochasticity since some trajectories, especially at T close to T_3 , must usually be repeated using different initial seeds to ensure the hydrate phase grows or melts. These repetitions are unnecessary for the simulations for calculating solubilities if the systems are well equilibrated. In any case there is no free lunch and the method is also expensive. The efficiency of both routes is similar in terms of computer time, with the solubility route being slightly less demanding. Nevertheless, both routes are correct and should lead to a consistent values of T_3 .

Notice that from a thermodynamic point of view above T_3 there should be no hydrate, and the reason why we can observe it is because the nucleation of the gas phase is an activated process. On the other hand below T_3 one of the two phases (either water or methane depending on their relative amounts) should not exist. One should expect the nucleation of the hydrate, and then the growth of the hydrate until one of the two components (either water or methane) is totally consumed (see Fig. 1 of Ref. 10). The reason why we can evaluate the solubilities under metastable conditions⁷² is because the nucleation of either the hydrate or the gas are activated processes that do not take place in the time window (500 ns) required to determine the solubility with high accuracy. We confirmed that in the simulations used to determine the solubilities no nucleation of a hydrate was observed.

III.D. Revisiting T_3 from direct coexistence methods

For the system considered in this work Conde and Vega¹⁰ by using the three phases direct coexistence method obtained T_3 of 302 and 297 K respectively using two different system sizes and much shorter runs. It is of interest to revisit these calculations. For that purpose we have used a three phase system with the hydrate, water and the gas phase. Interfaces were parallel to the XY plane. The system consisted of 5944 water molecules and 1512 methane molecules and the size of the simulation box was equal to about $4.8 \times 4.8 \times 12.2$ nm³. Simulation were carried for a few temperatures in a range of 290 - 298 K. In order to maintain constant pressure, anisotropic scaling of the box was applied. The three-phase systems was prepared in order to determine the temperature of coexistence of three phases at the pressure of 400 bar. In order to accomplish that, the changes in time of the amount of the solid phase in the system at different temperatures was evaluated, with the use of the $\bar{\eta}_3$ order parameter (see Section S1 of Supporting Information for additional information). The temperature of the three phases coexistence was determined as an average of the lowest temperature at which the melting of

the solid phase was observed and the highest temperature at which the hydrate was seen to grow. Results for the evolution of the number of solid molecules are presented in Fig. 5. For temperatures above 296 K the hydrate phase melts whereas for temperatures below 292 K it grows. For the temperatures 293, 294 and 295 K the system with the three phases remains stable even after runs of the order of a microsecond. As can be seen the results of this work suggest 294(2) K as the value of T_3 for this system from direct coexistence simulations which is consistent with the value 297(2) K obtained from the solubility calculations using the cutoff of 9 Å or the value of 295 K using a cutoff of 17 Å. With all these results we recommend 295(2) K as the temperature of T_3 for this system.

FIG. 5. Time evolution of the size of the largest solid cluster at $p = 400$ bar for several temperatures as obtained from direct coexistence simulations of the hydrate-water-gas system. The hydrate melts clearly at 298 and 296 K. The hydrate grows at 290 and 292 K. Results at 293, 294 and 295 K do not show clear evidence of melting or growing suggesting a triple point temperature $T_3=294(2)$ K at 400 bar. Notice that close to T_3 the behavior is somewhat stochastic. In fact, at T_3 probability of melting or growing should be around fifty per cent.

In Table 2 the values of T_3 reported by various authors for the same model TIP4P/Ice and a LJ center for methane are presented. As can be seen there is some scatter, some of which results from different values of cutoffs used in the simulations. The two calculations of this work are in agreement with the error bar. Taking all factors into consideration our current estimated value is 295(2) K. This value (with its error bar) is consistent with a number of previous studies^{14,16–18,73} (some studies provide slightly higher value and others slightly lower) although certainly lower than the value reported by Jensen et al.¹⁵ and lower than one of the values reported by Conde and Vega.¹⁰

The value of this work is also in good agreement with the experimental value of T_3 at 400 bar, which is equal

to 297 K.⁷⁴ As it was shown before,⁷⁵ water models with melting points of ice close to the experimental value give good values of T_3 , which is further confirmed in this work.

TABLE 2. Values of T_3 at $p=400$ bar for the model considered in this work (TIP4P/Ice and a LJ center for methane) as obtained in this work from two different routes and as obtained from other authors. All results of the Table were obtained from direct coexistence method whereas that of Waage et al. was obtained from free energy calculations (we interpolated the results for 100 and 500 bar from these authors). The first two values are not compatible with the results of this work (even considering the combined error bars).

T_3 /K	Ref.	Cut-off used
302(3)	Conde and Vega ¹⁰	0.9 nm
314(7)	Jensen et al. ¹⁵	1.0 nm
297(8)	Conde and Vega ¹⁰	0.9 nm
293.4(9)	Michalis et al. ¹⁴	1.1 nm
293.5(5)	Fernandez-Fernandez et al. ¹⁶	1.1 nm
290.5(5)	Fernandez-Fernandez et al. ¹⁶	1.1 nm
291(3)	Tung et al. ¹⁷	0.95 nm
297.8	Waage et al. ¹⁸	1.0 nm
297(2)	Solubility calculations. This work	0.9 nm
295(2)	Solubility calculations. This work	1.7 nm
294(2)	Direct coexistence. This work	0.9 nm
295(2)	Recommended value. This work.	

III.E. Curvature effects on the solubility of methane from the gas phase

In Section III.A we have evaluated the solubility of methane in water from the gas phase when there is a planar interface between the aqueous solution and the gas phase. However, one could have a curved interface between the two phases and that could modify the value of the solubility. To analyze this we have prepared bubbles of different sizes and inserted them into an aqueous phase having around 5000 molecules of water (the number of molecules of methane was different depending on the size of the bubble and the thermodynamic conditions but was in the range of 400-700). The simulation box was cubic and we used isotropic NpT simulations. The system consists of a bubble of methane in the center of the simulation box (notice that the bubble is subject to Brownian motion and it can certainly move) surrounded by water. Radial density profiles of methane around the center of mass of the bubble were computed. The position of the center of mass of the bubble was evaluated separately in every frame of the trajectory based on the locations of the density maxima of methane in the X, Y and Z directions as was done in our previous work with LJ bubbles.^{76,77}

Simulations were performed for 500 ns and averages were obtained over the last 250 ns. Notice that the bubbles were stable all along the simulation. Once the

system reaches the equilibrium it is possible to compute the solubility of methane for this spherical (gas-water) interface. Notice that when the system reaches equilibrium the chemical potential of methane and water are identical in the two phases, and the same is true for all temperatures. However, pressure is now an inhomogeneous property and is different in the two phases. The condition of chemical equilibrium for this spherical interface is now written as:

$$\mu_{CH_4}^I(p^I, T, x_{CH_4}^I) = \mu_{CH_4}^{II}(p^{II}, T, x_{CH_4}^{II}) \quad (9)$$

$$\mu_{H_2O}^I(p^I, T, x_{CH_4}^I) = \mu_{H_2O}^{II}(p^{II}, T, x_{CH_4}^{II}) \quad (10)$$

For convenience when having a spherical interface, the aqueous solution will be denoted as phase I whereas the gas phase forming the bubble will be denoted as phase II. Before continuing it is important to clarify some aspects about the pressure in inhomogeneous systems. It is possible to define locally (at each point in space) a pressure tensor using, for instance, the Irving-Kirkwood (IK) criteria or that proposed by Harasima (H) (there is no unique way of locally defining the pressure tensor).⁶⁵ In an homogeneous system the pressure tensor is identical in all points of the sample. However, this is not the case in an inhomogeneous system. It is interesting to point out that the average value of a certain component of the pressure tensor in the entire system does not depend on the choice (IK or H) used to define it locally. The second interesting point is that for a system with a spherical interface (i.e bubble) the average of the trace of the pressure tensor in the entire system is identical to the pressure of the external phase (see Appendix of Reference 78 for a proof of this which follows from the condition of mechanical equilibrium⁷⁹ that states that the divergence of the pressure tensor should be zero $\nabla \cdot p = \mathbf{0}$). In short, in an inhomogeneous system the pressure of the system (i.e the average of the trace of the pressure tensor) is identical to the pressure of the external phase (i.e the aqueous solution in this case) and corresponds to the pressure applied by the isotropic barostat.

In Fig. 6 the density profile of methane is shown (in units of mass per unit of volume) as a function of the distance from the center of the bubble (denoted as R). As can be seen the bubble has a certain size which will be assigned as R_{bubble} . There is not a unique criteria⁶⁵ to define the radius of a bubble (we shall discuss this issue in detail later). For the time being we shall use a simple criteria.

We shall determine the radius of the bubble R_{bubble} as the value of R at which the density of methane in the density profile is just the arithmetic average of the density of methane in water and in the bubble. In previous work^{76,77} dealing with bubbles within a liquid for

FIG. 6. Density profile at 260 K of a bubble with radius 1.50 nm. The vertical line is the radius of the bubble as obtained from the equidensity criteria (i.e when the density of methane is simply the average of the values inside and outside the bubble).

the Lennard-Jones system we denoted this radius as the Equidensity Radius R_{eq} . Mathematically R_{eq} is defined as:

$$\rho_{CH_4}(R_{eq}) = \frac{\rho_{CH_4}^I + \rho_{CH_4}^{II}}{2} \quad (11)$$

where ρ_{CH_4} is the density of methane, either in phase I or in phase II (right hand side) or in the density profile (left hand side).

In Table 3 the solubilities of methane for bubbles of different sizes are shown. Results are also included in Fig. 4. As can be seen reducing the size of the bubble at constant temperature and global pressure increases the solubility of methane. At 290 K a bubble of around 2 nm increases the solubility by a factor of two with respect to the planar interface. At 260 K bubbles between 1.5 and 1.35 nm increase the solubility of methane by a factor of four to five with respect to the planar interface. This is in agreement with results of previous work.²⁵

TABLE 3. Solubilities of methane in the aqueous phase when in contact with bubbles of radius R_{bubble} . The value infinity for the radius indicates a planar interface. Radius are given in nm.

T/K	R_{bubble}/nm	x_{CH_4}	$x_{CH_4}(R)/x_{CH_4}(\infty)$
250	1.77(3)	0.0553(28)	4.5
	∞	0.0123(46)	
260	1.35(1)	0.0464(9)	5.2
	1.49(2)	0.0419(14)	4.7
	1.98(1)	0.0303(13)	3.5
	∞	0.0089(3)	
290	1.78(1)	0.0137(7)	3.2
	2.12(1)	0.0116(2)	2.7
	∞	0.0043(7)	

The increase in solubility of methane in the presence of bubbles with respect to the planar interface at constant temperature can be explained easily by noting that the local pressure inside the bubbles is not 400 bar (i.e the pressure of the external phase) but higher as can be understood from the Laplace equation. Higher pressures mean higher chemical potentials and assuming ideal behavior for methane in water that also means higher molar fraction. Let us try to understand the values obtained of the solubility on a theoretical basis. Let us assume that the chemical potential of methane in the water phase (phase I in our case) can be described as:

$$\mu_{CH_4}^I = \mu_{CH_4}^0 + kT \ln(\gamma_{CH_4}^I x_{CH_4}^I) \quad (12)$$

where $\mu_{CH_4}^0$ is just the standard state of methane in water which depends only on T and p but not on composition. By assuming ideal behavior (which seems reasonable taking into account the low solubility of methane in water) the change in the chemical potential of methane in the aqueous phase when in contact with a spherical bubble and with a planar interface can be estimated approximately (i.e neglecting changes in the activity coefficient) as:

$$\mu_{CH_4}^I(bubble) - \mu_{CH_4}^I(planar) \simeq kT \ln \left[\frac{x_{CH_4}^I(bubble)}{x_{CH_4}^I(planar)} \right] \quad (13)$$

Since the solubility can change by a factor of 5 the chemical potential of methane changes significantly when in presence of bubbles (around 1.6 in $k_B T$ units). Estimates of the chemical potential obtained from this route are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4. Radius of the bubble (as given by R_{eq}) and chemical potential of methane in the bubble (with respect to the the chemical potential of bulk methane at 400 bar). Thermodynamic pressure inside the bubble (i.e the value of the pressure of a bulk phase of methane having the same chemical potential as that found in the bubble). Interfacial free energy between the bubble and the aqueous phase (in mJ/m^2) as estimated from the Laplace equation assuming the equi-density radius R_{eq} is the radius at the surface of tension^{65,80} R_s .

T/K	R_{bubble}/nm	$\Delta\mu_{CH_4}/k_B T$	$p^{II,\mu}/\text{bar}$	$\sigma_s/\text{mJ}/\text{m}^2$
(eq. 13)				
250	1.77(3)	1.50(6)	1062(25)	58.59
260	1.35(1)	1.65(2)	1147(9)	50.42
	1.49(2)	1.56(2)	1103(8)	52.37
	1.98(1)	1.22(4)	936(19)	53.06
290	1.78(1)	1.16(5)	859(21)	40.85
	2.12(1)	0.98(2)	785(5)	40.81

It is interesting to determine what would be the pressure of a bulk phase of methane needed to have the same chemical potential as methane in the external phase. We shall call that the thermodynamic pressure $p^{II,\mu}$ of the phase II. This pressure can be obtained easily by integrating (along an isotherm) the volume per molecule of pure methane:

$$\mu_{CH_4}^I(bubble) - \mu_{CH_4}^I(planar) = \int_{p=400\text{bar}}^{p^{II,\mu}} (V/N) dp \quad (14)$$

where the integrand (V/N) is the volume per molecule of a bulk phase of methane at pressure p, which can be obtained easily from simulations of pure bulk methane in the NpT ensemble. Notice that this thermodynamic pressure $p^{II,\mu}$ is the one that enters into the thermodynamic description of the internal phase in Gibbsian formalism (in Section S2 of Supporting Information we discuss this issue further). Results for this thermodynamic pressure are presented in Table 4.

Finally we can estimate a value of σ_s for the bubble-water interface using the Laplace equation

$$p^{II,\mu} - 400 = 2\sigma_s/R_s \quad (15)$$

where R_s is the radius at the surface of tension⁸⁰ and σ_s is the interfacial free energy at the surface of tension (see references 65, 80, and 81 for a detailed description of all the subtle issues concerning the thermodynamics of curved interfaces and a proof that the Laplace equation only holds when the dividing surface is located at the radius of tension). In general the value of R_s is unknown as its determination requires free energy calculations. However, if one assumes that

$$R_{eq} \simeq R_s \quad (16)$$

then one can obtain values of σ_s . They are shown in Table 4. As can be seen the value of σ_s is different from that of a planar interface as also found in other systems.^{82,83} We found that the value of σ_s for the bubbles of this work are around 10 to 20 percent lower than that of the planar interface. That indicates a positive Tolman length for the methane-water interface.⁸³ Similar decrease in the value of γ for small LJ droplets was found by Vrabec et al.⁸⁴

One may wonder if it would be possible to increase the solubility of methane beyond a factor of 5-6 with respect to the value of the planar interface by making the bubbles even smaller. We have attempted to do that by removing particles of methane from the bubbles to make them smaller. However, unfortunately at around 1.25 nm they become mechanically unstable and disappear by dissolving into the water phase. Thus it is not possible to increase the solubility of methane with respect to that of the planar phase up to an arbitrary limit. It seems it is only possible to increase the solubility by a factor of 4-6 by using bubbles slightly above the nanometer size.

III.F. Curvature effects on the solubility of methane from the hydrate phase

It seems of interest to now compute the solubility of methane in water when in contact with the hydrate, but now with a spherical interface. For that purpose we shall insert a spherical solid cluster of the hydrate solid phase into a cubic box of water with some methane previously dissolved. It was observed that for certain concentrations of methane in solution the solid cluster was fairly stable. In fact, after running over 1 μ s, the size of the cluster did not change much and fluctuated around an average value. To determine the size of the cluster we used the order parameter proposed by Lechner and Dellago.⁵⁶ In particular we used \bar{q}_3 . Details are described in the Supporting Information. The time evolution of the size of the cluster is shown in Fig. 7. As can be seen the cluster remains stable. The concentration of methane in the external phase was constant and its value was 0.0046 (in molar fraction) which is about five times higher than the solubility of the hydrate when in a planar interface.

The physics is quite similar to that found for bubbles. The presence of curvature increases the solubility of methane from the hydrate. One can understand that again by regarding the Laplace equation and understanding that the spherical solid cluster is at higher pressure, therefore the chemical potential of the methane increases and so does the solubility. A similar effect was found in a previous study determining the solubility of NaCl in water or that of a LJ solid into the fluid both for planar and curved interfaces.⁸⁵ The solubility of the spherical solid was higher than that of the planar interface. It is nice to know that the solubility increases with the presence

FIG. 7. Time evolution of the size of the spherical solid cluster of hydrate at 250 K and 400 bar, for the system consisting of 4786 molecules of water and 200 molecules of methane. As can be seen the cluster is stable and neither grows nor melts. The concentration of methane in the aqueous solution is presented as a light blue filled square at 250 K in Fig.4.

of curvature, but one should be aware that to determine the solubility of a certain force field one should always use the planar interface.

III.G. Stability of inhomogeneity in a finite size system

It is well known that for one component systems it is possible in certain ensembles (for instance NVT) to have a stable inhomogeneous system.⁸⁶ Depending on the values of N , V and T one can find inhomogeneous systems with spherical, cylindrical or planar interfaces as the most stable ones (i.e at the absolute minimum of the Helmholtz free energy F).^{76,77,86,87} One can even have local minima in F which are metastable with respect to others (i.e a system with a spherical interface which is metastable with respect to a cylindrical or planar interface).⁸⁸ These local minima can be separated by free energy barriers so that one can stay in these minima for a long time. However, for pure components, as soon as one switches to the NpT ensemble the inhomogeneous system is unstable^{87,89} and it will evolve towards one of the two phases at equilibrium (regardless of whether one has a spherical, cylindrical or planar interface). The summary is that in pure components the existence of a stable (or metastable) inhomogeneous system is possible in the NVT ensemble (see Ref. 88 for a discussion of whether this is also possible for other ensembles).

What is the situation for mixtures? A finite size mixture is defined by four variables. For instance one could use N_1 , N_2 , p and T as in our NpT simulations. The main difference between a mixture and a pure component system is that now an inhomogeneous system (with a planar or curved interface) can be at equilibrium (either stable or metastable) in the N_1N_2pT ensemble. Thus the inhomogeneous system will be stable/metastable as it would live in a global/local minima of the Gibbs free energy G .

Obviously the inhomogeneous system will be unstable if one changes to the semigrand-ensemble⁹⁰ where N_1 , μ_2 , p and T are constant as it will evolve towards one of the two phases at equilibrium. Thus for mixtures N_1N_2pT follow the behavior of NVT in pure component systems, and $N_1\mu_2pT$ follow the behavior of the NpT in pure component systems.

The message is that for a certain value of N_1 , N_2 , p and T one can have local minima of G describing either a homogeneous system, or several inhomogeneous systems with spherical, cylindrical or planar interfaces. In general there would be free energy barriers separating these states. If the free energy barriers are large the system can stay for quite long times in these configurations. If the free energy barriers are small the system will overcome these free energy barriers and will evolve to the global minima in G . It goes beyond this study to analyze if the curved interfaces considered so far (for instance that of the spherical solid cluster of hydrate in equilibrium with the solution shown in Fig. 7) correspond to the absolute minima in G for the selected values of N_1 , N_2 , p and T . It is clear that if they are stable for quite long times (i.e. larger than 500 ns) they correspond to local minima in G .

Now we shall analyze in detail the thermodynamic driving force for the formation of the solid hydrate.

III.H. Driving force for nucleation of hydrates

Below T_3 one should not have water in contact with methane (regardless of whether one has planar or curved interfaces). One should have the hydrate in contact with either water or the gas. If the ratio $N_{H_2O}/N_{CH_4} > 5.75$ one should have an hydrate-water system. If the ratio is smaller one should have a hydrate-gas phase system. The formation of the hydrate in the aqueous phase can be written as a chemical reaction (see Kashchiev and Firoozabadi²²) occurring at constant p and T :

It is useful to treat the hydrate as a new compound which has one molecule of methane and 5.75 of water and to define a chemical potential for the hydrate. Obviously the chemical potential of the hydrate is just the sum of the chemical potential of methane in the solid plus 5.75 times the chemical potential of water in the solid. If one is interested in changes in the stoichiometry of the hydrate then one should refer to the chemical potential of the individual components of the solid. However, the occupancy of methane cages is large (usually well above 90 percent) and we shall assume here full occupancy (further work is needed to understand if the non stoichiometry is due to either thermodynamics or kinetic reasons). We shall assume here that all cages of the hydrate are occupied by

methane. Therefore we shall refer to the chemical potential of the hydrate (and not to the chemical potential of its individual species). This is analogous to the case of NaCl in the solid phase. One could refer to the chemical potential of Na and Cl individually but it is more useful to evaluate the chemical potential of NaCl in the solid phase (which of course is just the sum of the chemical potentials of the individual ions). Therefore the compound $[\text{CH}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{5.75}]_{solid}$ will be denoted simply as the "hydrate" and one molecule of the hydrate means one molecule of $[\text{CH}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{5.75}]$ in the solid.

What is the value of the driving force for nucleation of the hydrate from the solution? We shall denote it as $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ and it is given by:^{22,23}

$$\Delta\mu_{nucleation} = \mu_{hydrate} - \mu_{CH_4}(aq, x_{CH_4}) - 5.75 \mu_{H_2O}(aq, x_{CH_4}) \quad (18)$$

where it should be understood that each individual chemical potential is computed at the same p and T . Obviously the value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ depends also on the value of the variable x_{CH_4} . There is a particular value of x_{CH_4} of great interest from a practical point of view. It corresponds to the case in which the value of x_{CH_4} is given by the solubility of methane from the gas phase (unless otherwise stated, via a planar interface). This is the way experiments on the nucleation of hydrate are performed (i.e. a water phase in contact via a planar interface with the gas phase of methane). We shall denote this value simply as $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ (where the superindex EC indicates Experimental Conditions). Notice that in this case the value of x_{CH_4} is not an independent variable as it is entirely determined by p and T . The chemical potential of the hydrate does not depend on composition and is also entirely determined by p and T . Unfortunately very little is known on the experimental values of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$. Kashchiev and Firoozabadi used experimental information to roughly evaluate its magnitude.^{22,23} It seems of interest to determine it for the force field used in this work. It could be useful for future studies of nucleation using the same force field. It can also provide clear trends of the experimental values. However, force fields are approximate so that the obtained values will not be identical to those found in experiments.

III.H.1. Route 1 to $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$

Let us estimate $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ which by definition is $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ when the molar fraction of methane is given by the solubility of methane from the gas phase via a planar interface. We shall illustrate how to compute it along the $p=400$ bar isobar. The first route to $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ is simple: one will evaluate each of the terms of Eq. 18 individually and then one will compute $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$. When evaluated in this way it will be denoted as $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$. At T_3 for 400 bar we know that $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC} = 0$ (i.e.

the chemical potential of methane and water in the solution and in the hydrate are identical) although we do not know the individual values of μ_{CH_4} and μ_{H_2O} . However, this is not a problem as we are interested in changes in chemical potentials and not in individual values. For this reason we shall set to zero the chemical potential of methane, water and hydrate at T_3 (i.e. 295 K).

To estimate $\mu_{CH_4}(aq, x_{CH_4})$ we shall use Eq. 6 which is almost exact as the solubility of water in the methane gas phase is negligible. The calculation of $\mu_{hydrate}$ is both simple and exact and is given by:

$$\mu_{hydrate}(T)/(k_B T) = - \int_{T_3}^T \frac{h_{hydrate}}{kT'^2} dT' \quad (19)$$

where $h_{hydrate}$ is the enthalpy of one "molecule" of the hydrate (i.e the $CH_4(H_2O)_{5.75}$).

To evaluate $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ we also need to evaluate $\mu_{H_2O}(aq, p, T, x_{CH_4})$. Let us write the expression of the chemical potential of water in the solution at T_3 and at T .

$$\mu_{H_2O}(p, T_3, x_{H_2O}(p, T_3)) = \mu_{H_2O}^*(p, T_3) + kT_3 \ln(\gamma_{H_2O} x_{H_2O}(p, T_3)) \quad (20)$$

where for simplicity we have omitted the dependence of γ with T , p and the composition. Since the solution is diluted one may approximate the value of γ_{H_2O} to one to obtain:

$$\mu_{H_2O}(p, T_3, x_{H_2O}(p, T_3)) = \mu_{H_2O}^*(p, T_3) + kT_3 \ln(x_{H_2O}(p, T_3)) \quad (21)$$

Let us now write the same expression at T :

$$\mu_{H_2O}(p, T, x_{H_2O}(p, T)) = \mu_{H_2O}^*(p, T) + kT \ln(x_{H_2O}(p, T)) \quad (22)$$

Therefore the change in chemical potential along the isobar is obtained as:

$$\mu_{H_2O}(p, T, x_{H_2O}(p, T)) - \mu_{H_2O}(p, T_3, x_{H_2O}(p, T_3)) = C_1 + C_2 \quad (23)$$

$$C_1 = [\mu_{H_2O}^*(p, T) - \mu_{H_2O}^*(p, T_3)] \quad (24)$$

$$C_2 = [kT \ln(x_{H_2O}(p, T)) - kT_3 \ln(x_{H_2O}(p, T_3))] \quad (25)$$

As can be seen the chemical potential has two contributions (each of the square brackets on the right hand side of the previous equation). The first one accounts for changes in the chemical potential of pure water due to the temperature and the second one for changes in the molar fraction of water. Since the standard state for

water is pure water one simply obtains (h_{H_2O} being the enthalpy per particle of pure liquid water) :

$$C1 = - \int_{T_3}^T \frac{h_{H_2O}}{kT'^2} dT' \quad (26)$$

The second contribution is quite small and can be either neglected or estimated from the solubility of methane in water. Notice that the change in chemical potential is also the chemical potential of water at T as the chemical potential of water was set to zero at T_3 . The route of obtaining $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$ is schematically depicted in Fig. 8a.

FIG. 8. Schematic depiction of two routes for obtaining $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$. The points represent the equilibrium concentrations of methane in water in a gas-liquid (light blue points) and hydrate-liquid (orange point) systems with a planar interface at temperature T . a) Route 1 to $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$. b) Route 2 to $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2}$.

As has been discussed above to evaluate $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$ simulations of pure methane, pure water and pure hydrate are needed. In the case of pure methane and pure water a cubic system having 1000 molecules will

be used. In the case of the pure hydrate a system having 1242 molecules of water and 216 methane will be used. Isotropic NpT simulations will be performed for pure water and pure methane. For the hydrate we used anisotropic NpT scaling (although as the solid has cubic structure isotropic scaling would have also been possible). Systems were simulated at a few temperatures in the range 250-310 K for 100 ns.

Values of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$ are presented in Fig. 9. As can be seen for a supercooling of about 35 K (i.e 260 K) it amounts to around 2.3 in $k_B T$ units. Using experimental results Kashchiev and Firoozabadi²² estimated a value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ of about 1.5 $k_B T$ at the pressure of 194 bar for a supercooling of 20 K (see Fig. 4 of Ref. 22). We have included this result in Fig. 9 and as it can be seen our results are consistent with those of Kashchiev and Firoozabadi (although our values are for the force field of this work and those of Kashchiev and Firoozabadi for experiments and in addition both results were obtained at different pressures). Notice that to evaluate $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ Kashchiev and Firoozabadi needed to estimate a number of properties for the hydrate and for the pure components.

FIG. 9. Chemical potential for hydrate formation $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$ and $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2}$ as a function of temperature along the 400 bar isobar. For the first route we use 295 K as the value for T_3 . Obviously at this temperature $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ is zero as the three phases are in equilibrium. Results assuming $T_3 = 293$ K and $T_3 = 297$ K are also shown. The results include the small correction due to the change in molar fraction of water with temperature (Eq. 25). To obtain the values of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2}$ we fitted the solubility values for temperatures in the range of 260-300 K to curves, which are given by: $x_{CH_4} = e^{-0.0332 \cdot T + 3.744} + 0.00135$ for the gas-liquid system and $x_{CH_4} = e^{-0.0622 \cdot T - 24.268} + 0.0005$ for the hydrate-liquid system. Values of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2}$ were determined using the runs with the cutoff of 9 Å leading to $T_3 = 297$ K (for this reason the agreement is better with $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$ obtained for this choice of T_3). For comparison we have also included (red point) the value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ estimated from experimental results by Kashchiev and Firoozabadi^{22,23} at 194 bar and for a supercooling of 20 K with respect to the T_3 at this pressure.

In Table 5 the individual contributions to $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$ are provided. It is clear that the major contribution is made by the hydrate and water. The methane contributes in a much smaller magnitude to $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$.

TABLE 5. Chemical potential change of hydrate formation under experimental condition (i.e. x_{CH_4} given by the gas-liquid equilibrium with a flat interface) evaluated from the first route $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$ at 400 bar for several temperatures. At the T_3 , i.e 295 K the chemical potential of all species was set to zero.

T/K	5.75 ×			$\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC1}$
	$\Delta\mu(CH_4(aq))$	$\Delta\mu(H_2O(aq))$	$\Delta\mu(hydrate)$	
250	-0.13639	-23.34586	-26.62722	-3.14497
260	-0.09386	-17.33869	-19.85317	-2.42062
270	-0.05914	-11.84815	-13.61482	-1.70753
280	-0.03118	-6.81213	-7.85394	-1.01062
290	-0.00909	-2.17910	-2.52036	-0.33217
295	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Let us finish this section by presenting a quite simple (but approximate) route to determine $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ by using the dissociation enthalpy of the hydrate. The dissociation enthalpy h_{diss} is defined as the enthalpy change of the process:

When calculating dissociation enthalpies one assumes that the hydrate dissociates into pure water and pure methane. Of course although this is the definition of the enthalpy of dissociation one should keep in mind that when the actual hydrate dissociates there will always be a small amount of methane dissolved into water and an even smaller amount of water dissolved in the methane gas phase. The dissociation enthalpy of the model used in this work is obtained simply by performing simulations of the pure phases (hydrate, water and methane) at several temperatures along the isobar. Dissociation enthalpies obtained from simulations are reported in Table 6.

TABLE 6. Dissociation enthalpy (per mol of methane) of the hydrate at several temperatures at 400 bar.

T/K	$\Delta h_{diss} / k_B T$	$\Delta h_{diss} / kJ/mol$
250	18.53	38.51
260	18.94	40.92
270	19.26	43.23
280	19.38	45.11
290	19.59	47.22
295	19.62	48.12
300	19.68	49.07
310	19.72	50.81

The values obtained are in good agreement with previously reported values for a similar system.⁹⁸ Notice that one can obtain a simple (but approximate) expression to estimate the value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ by assuming that the enthalpy of dissociation does not change with temperature and can be taken from its value at T_3 $h_{diss}^{T_3}$ and by neglecting the change in composition with temperature of the aqueous solution containing methane thus obtaining :

$$\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{quasi-EC} = k_B T \int_{T_3}^T \frac{h_{diss}}{kT'^2} dT' \simeq \simeq -h_{diss}^{T_3} (1 - T/T_3) \quad (28)$$

The values obtained from this route are included in Fig. 10. The agreement with the more elaborate expression of Eq. 18 is good although starts to deviate at large supercoolings.

FIG. 10. Values of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ as obtained from assuming constant enthalpy of dissociation (Eq.28) as compared to the more elaborated Eq.18. We used the value 295K for T_3 at 400 bar.

Let us now present another possible route to estimate $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$.

III.H.2. Obtaining $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ from values of the solubility of methane

In the previous route we arrived to the state of interest with p , T and $x_{CH_4} = x_{CH_4}(aq, p, T|gas)$ along an isobar starting from a point where the chemical potential of water and methane was identical in the solution and in the hydrate. But it is also possible to arrive to the state p and T and composition x_{CH_4} arriving from another state with the same p and T but with different composition and where the chemical potential of methane and water are identical in the solution and in the hydrate. In

fact, along the solubility curve of methane from the hydrate this conditions is satisfied so that $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC} = 0$. Therefore we just need to compute the change in chemical potential with composition at constant p and T . Notice that standard states depend only on p and T and not on composition, and since the hydrate chemical potential does not change when changing the composition of the solution one obtains a new route to determine (labeled with the superindex 2) $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2}$:

$$\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2} = k_B T \left[-\ln \left(\frac{x_{CH_4}(aq, p, T|gas)}{x_{CH_4}(aq, p, T|hydrate)} \right) - 5.75 \ln \left(\frac{x_{H_2O}(aq, p, T|gas)}{x_{H_2O}(aq, p, T|hydrate)} \right) \right] \quad (29)$$

where the vertical lines represents flat interface equilibrium with another phase (i.e gas methane or the solid hydrate). This route for obtaining $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2}$ is depicted in Fig. 8b. The negative sign arises from the fact that we have defined $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ in the direction of freezing so that one subtracts the chemical potential of methane and water in the aqueous solution. Since the solubility of methane is quite small, the molar fraction of water is close to 1 and one can neglect the second term on the right hand side. This was done by Molinero and coworkers⁸ in previous work.

The values of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2}$ obtained from this second route are shown in Fig. 9 and they are compared to the ones of the first route. The agreement is quite good. Notice, however, that the shape of the curves obtained by EC1 and EC2 routes is slightly different (a curvature of the line obtained by the EC2 route can be seen). The reason for that is presumably related to the uncertainty of the values of solubilities used to calculate $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2}$ - as can be seen in Fig. 1 and Fig. 3, there is some scatter in the results. Additionally, the solubility of methane in water when in contact with the hydrate is very low at low temperatures and even small error may have significant impact on the value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC2}$.

In previous work we have determined values of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ for the formation of ice Ih (for a pure substance the value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ is unique as one does not need to specify the composition of the aqueous phase). For instance for a supercooling of 35 K we found a value of 0.29 in $k_B T$ units.⁹¹ At the same supercooling the chemical potential change per unit of hydrate molecule is around 2.30 $k_B T$ which after being divided by 5.75 yields a value of 0.40 $k_B T$ per molecule of water. The summary is that the driving force for the nucleation of the methane hydrate (at 400 bar) is significantly higher than that of the nucleation of ice (at 1 bar) when compared at the same supercooling. Other things being equal (i.e interfacial energies) that means that nucleation of the hydrate should be more favorable than that of ice Ih.⁹²

III.1. Helping hydrate nucleation

In the previous section we have shown how to compute $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$ for hydrate nucleation under "experimental conditions", i.e $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$. By experimental conditions we mean that the concentration of methane in water is that obtained at equilibrium for a planar water-gas interface at the considered values of p and T.

Would it be possible to help the nucleation of hydrate under "special conditions"? The answer to this question is positive. In fact, for certain values of p and T by using brute force simulation Sum and coworkers²⁵ were able to nucleate the hydrate in less than a microsecond (provided that the gas phase was forming a bubble and the concentration of methane in water was in the range x_{CH_4} 0.02-0.04). At the same conditions of p and T nucleation never occurred for the planar interface even after running several microseconds. Definitely the bubbles helped and the reason is simple. The solubility of methane increases. We shall denote as $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^*$ (with an asterisk) values of the change in chemical potential for the formation of the hydrate (i.e values of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}$) obtained at conditions where the solubility of methane is higher than that obtained for a planar water-gas interface at the considered conditions of p and T (for example when one has a bubble of methane and not a planar interface). For simplicity, we shall denote as $x_{CH_4}^{eq}$ and $x_{H_2O}^{eq}$ the molar fractions of methane and water in the aqueous phase when in equilibrium with the gas phase via a planar interface at a certain value of p and T. We shall denote $x_{CH_4}^*$ and $x_{H_2O}^*$ values of the molar fractions in the aqueous phase different from these. If the composition of the aqueous solution is changed but p and T are unchanged then the chemical potential of the hydrate phase does not change. However, there will be a change in the chemical potential of water and methane. One then obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\mu_{nucleation}^* &= \Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC} - k_B T \ln \left(\frac{x_{CH_4}^*}{x_{CH_4}^{eq}} \right) \\ &\quad - 5.75 k_B T \ln \left(\frac{x_{H_2O}^*}{x_{H_2O}^{eq}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

If we neglect the third term on the right hand side (which is typically much smaller than the second one as molar fractions of water in solution are typically above 0.95) then one obtains:

$$\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^* = \Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC} - k_B T \ln \left(\frac{x_{CH_4}^*}{x_{CH_4}^{eq}} \right) \quad (31)$$

According to this expression if the solubility of methane is increased by a factor of 3-5 then the value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^*$ becomes larger (in absolute value as it is a negative number) by 1.1-1.6 $k_B T$ units with respect to $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$. This is quite a significant increase. Around

20 K of additional supercooling would be needed to obtain a similar change in $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$. Of course 20 K of further supercooling slows down all the dynamics. Therefore bubbles help in the nucleation of the hydrate and would provoke a similar increase in the driving force as 20 K of further supercooling while keeping the dynamics fast. However, there is a limit in the help that bubbles can provide for brute force nucleation studies. As bubbles can not be smaller than 1.25 nm (they are not mechanically stable for smaller sizes), then the maximum increase that they can provide for nucleation is of around 1.6 $k_B T$ units. This is enough to force nucleation for moderate to high supercooling (i.e in the range of T between 240 K and 255 K). However this is not enough to provoke spontaneous nucleation at small supercoolings (i.e above 260 K). In fact, for pressures below 500 bar Sum and coworkers^{25,26} were not able to nucleate hydrate at temperatures above 255 K even with bubbles.

Would it be possible to nucleate the hydrate at even higher temperatures (i.e above 260 K)? Bubbles are not enough but extra help can be found. In fact, all that is needed is to have an "artificially" high value of $x_{CH_4}^*$. A possibility is to start from a highly supersaturated solution (i.e one with a concentration many times higher than the solubility of the planar interface). The system would be now in a double metastable state. In fact, it will be metastable with respect to the formation of the hydrate, but it would be also metastable with respect to the formation of the gas phase (either in the form of bubbles, cylinders or a planar interface). The phase that will appear first is the one with the lowest free energy barrier for nucleation. This was the approach used by Sarupria and Debenedetti^{93,94} and it is also the path followed in pioneering studies on hydrate nucleation. We shall follow this approach. We will start from a homogeneous mixture having around 5000 molecules of water and the number of methane molecules required to have a certain molar fraction of methane. We typically used values of $x_{CH_4}^*$ in the range 0.042-0.117 (notice that 0.117 is only slightly below the composition of the hydrate which has a molar fraction of methane of around 0.16). Results of these runs are shown in Fig. 11. As can be seen we were able to observe the nucleation of the hydrates at all temperatures up to 285 K (i.e just 10 K below T_3 !). These results are in line with the results obtained previously⁹⁵ for similar system at p = 500 bar - in this case nucleation of hydrate was observed for temperatures in the range of 250-285 K (up to 19 K below T_3 for this pressure conditions).

At the temperature of 285 K the supersaturation needed to observe the nucleation is almost 20 times the equilibrium solubility for the planar interface. Such a supersaturation provokes a shift in the chemical potential of methane of about 3 $k_B T$ units. Since $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^{EC}$ at this T is of about 0.7 $k_B T$ it can be seen that a value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^*$ around 4 $k_B T$ is enough at this temperature to provoke nucleation in brute force runs. In general

values of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^*$ higher than $4 k_B T$ are enough to guarantee nucleation in brute force simulations. These values can be obtained below 255 K using bubbles, or above this temperature using highly supersaturated homogeneous solutions.

FIG. 11. Size of the largest solid cluster of hydrate as obtained in brute force NpT simulations ($p=400$ bar, cutoff = 9 \AA) of homogeneous solutions at different temperatures and supersaturations. The value of the equilibrium solubility of methane (for a planar interface) at each temperature is shown. The actual values of the molar fraction of methane of each run are also shown, as well as the supersaturation S defined as the ratio $x_{CH_4}^*/x_{CH_4}^{eq}$. We obtained spontaneous crystallization for all temperatures up to 10 degrees below T_3 .

It is worth to point out that the hydrate nucleation is a transition from a disordered phase to an ordered phase with solid-like characteristics that are not necessarily crystalline. In our work we were only interested in detecting the nucleation events, for which we used the $\overline{q_3}$ order parameter, while the details of the structure of the formed hydrate were not analysed.

We tried to obtain nucleation even at higher temperatures (i.e around 290 K) using high supersaturation. However, we were not successful. If the supersaturation was low then there was no nucleation and if the supersaturation was high then the spontaneous formation of the bubbles of the gas phase took place and supersaturation was reduced to normal (i.e. 3-5 times) which is not enough to induce nucleation at these high temperatures close to the T_3 . We also observed the formation of bubbles at lower temperatures (i.e 270-285 K), but only for the highest concentration of methane considered - $x_{CH_4} = 0.117$. At 270 K both the hydrate and the bubble were formed at the beginning of the simulation, however the hydrate melted soon after. Although it is not an accurate method to determine T_3 it is obvious that the highest temperature at which spontaneous formation of the hydrate was observed in a highly supersaturated solution provides a lower bound to a rough estimate of T_3 .

We must confess that we never succeed in forming ice Ih in brute force simulations of pure water using the TIP4P/Ice model. The fact that we are able to nucleate the hydrate in a few hundreds of ns while just 10 K below T_3 is remarkable. The concentration of methane in water is the key to change dramatically the driving force for nucleation. This can be increased either by introducing bubbles or by starting from an homogeneous highly supersaturated solution.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have studied at 400 bar the solubility of methane in water when in contact with either the gas or the hydrate with computer simulations using the TIP4P/Ice model for water and a simple LJ model to describe the methane molecule. The solubility of methane from the gas decreases as the temperature increases revealing that the process is exothermic. The solubility of methane from the hydrate increases with temperature showing that the process is endothermic. There is a temperature at which both curves intersect and this determines the T_3 at which the three phases: gas, water and hydrate can remain at equilibrium at a certain pressure. Therefore we show that a new method to evaluate T_3 in hydrate research is available and that requires to perform simulations that reach equilibrium in all the cases. Above T_3 the hydrate is not thermodynamically stable. Below T_3 one of the two fluid phases will not be thermodynamically stable. However, we observe metastability. Therefore it is possible to have a water-gas interface

at temperatures below T_3 as the formation of hydrate is an activated process, and it is also possible to have the hydrate-water interface as the formation of the gas phase is an activated process. Since there is some scatter around the value of T_3 for this system, we revisited also the direct coexistence method using larger systems than in our previous work. The final conclusion is that for this system the T_3 is located at 294(2) K from direct coexistence simulations and at 297(2) K for the solubility calculations (for a cutoff of 9 Å) and 295(2) K (for a cutoff of 17 Å). These values are lower than one of the values we reported some time ago (i.e 302 K) and in better agreement with the estimates of other groups. With all this information we suggest 295(2) K as the T_3 for this system at the pressure of 400 bar.

We have analyzed the impact of curved interface on the solubility of methane concluding that curvature increases the solubility. Both the solubility of methane from the gas and the solubility of methane from the hydrate increase due to curvature. The explanation is simple, the higher pressure inside the phase forming the sphere increase its chemical potential and therefore increases the solubility (as can be understood by describing the behavior of methane in water by an ideal mixture model with activity coefficient equal to one). We have estimated the change in chemical potential of methane due to curvature. The fact that bubbles increase the solubility has been described previously. We show here that the smallest bubble that is mechanically stable has a radius of about 1.25 nm. Below this size the bubbles collapse. Therefore by using bubbles one can increase the solubility of methane with respect to a planar interface by a maximum factor of 4-6. It is not possible to increase the solubility beyond this value. However, the fact that it is possible to have stable solid clusters of the hydrate in contact with the solution has not been reported before. The existence of spherical stable interfaces in the NVT ensemble for pure components has been described before for HS (solid-fluid) and LJ systems (both solid-fluid and fluid-fluid). For pure components it is not possible to have a stable spherical interface in the NpT ensemble. Here we show that this is possible for mixtures, and not only for the gas-water interface but also for the hydrate-water interface.

The driving force for nucleation is the change in chemical potential when forming the hydrate. There are almost no estimates of its value with the exception of the work of Kashchiev and Firoozabadi.^{22,23} Even from experiments it is difficult to estimate this magnitude due to the lack of many experimental results for some properties that are required to evaluate the change in chemical potential. Here we estimate the change in chemical potential by using an almost exact route. For methane and the hydrate we estimate the chemical potential exactly. For water it was necessary to assume ideal behavior of the aqueous solution of methane which seems reasonable given the low solubility of methane. We obtained the value of the change in chemical potential for the formation of the hy-

drate using two different thermodynamic routes obtaining values that are fully consistent. At a temperature of 260 K this change was of 2.3 in $k_B T$ units per molecule of hydrate (i.e $\text{CH}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{5.75}$). This is higher than the magnitude we found for ice formation for a supercooling of 35 K (when computed per molecule of water). We have also evaluated how this chemical potential is modified when the solubility of methane increases with respect to the value of the planar interface. By inserting methane bubbles into the solution we have shown that the chemical potential of methane increases by about 1.6 $k_B T$ units, inducing an increase in the driving force for nucleation that is comparable to that produced by 20 degrees of additional supercooling. That explains why nucleation of the hydrate in brute force simulations is much easier when having bubbles. However, one can go beyond the bubbles. In fact, one can start from an homogeneous solution of methane having a supersaturation in the range 5-10 (reaching molar fractions up to 0.117) and then hydrate formation is observed for temperatures up to 285 K (i.e just 10 K below the value of T_3). Notice that for the TIP4P/Ice model we were never able to obtain ice in brute force studies regardless of the temperature considered. Again the facility to nucleate hydrate now arises from the fact that although one can not modify much neither the chemical potential of the hydrate, nor that of water at a certain T and p, you can increase dramatically the chemical potential of methane by inducing supersaturation (i.e. higher concentrations than those of the planar interface) either by using bubbles or by starting from an homogeneous supersaturated solution. This increases the value of the driving force for nucleation in simulations (i.e the value of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^*$) thus reducing the free energy barrier which is proportional to the third power of the interfacial free energy and inversely proportional to the second power of $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^*$. Increasing $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^*$ by a factor of two reduces the free energy barrier by a factor of four. Since the free energy barrier enters in an exponential term when determining nucleation rates by CNT, the change in $\Delta\mu_{nucleation}^*$ provokes a dramatic change in the nucleation rates.

It was not possible to nucleate the hydrate at temperatures above 285 K in the homogeneous highly supersaturated system. This is so because the system is in a double metastable state (both with respect to the formation of hydrate and with respect to the formation of the bubble). The transition with the smallest value of the free energy barrier will take place first. It seems that for temperatures below 285 K the smaller free energy barrier corresponds to that of hydrate formation whereas for temperatures above that it corresponds to bubble formation. In experiment it is possible to nucleate hydrate at temperatures just below T_3 , however it is likely that in this case the process occurs via heterogeneous nucleation.

It is clear that a lot of physics can be learnt by studying the solubility of methane in water. Although the system is simple it contains a number of interesting features. In the future it would be of interest to determine in a quan-

titative way of estimating the nucleation rates for this system^{96,97} in conditions where brute force simulations are useless (due to the high induction time). What is clear now is that nucleation of hydrates can be either an event with almost zero probability or an event observed in just dozens of nanoseconds. The concentration of methane is the start of this movie. Somewhat surprisingly you can nucleate methane hydrates using the TIP4P/Ice model in brute force simulations, whereas this was never observed (to the best of our knowledge) for the formation of ice.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Description of the order parameter used in this work for identifying hydrate (Section S1); Pressure inside methane bubbles (Section S2) (PDF)

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